

How to FAIRify Citizen Science?

Using the Wikibase Ecosystem for Volunteered Cultural Heritage Information Systems

Florian Thierry M.Sc.

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13:30
60 min.

Keynote: On the role of Knowledge and Intelligence in the path from Thoughts to Actions

Keynote by Prof Dr Sahar Vahdati (45 mins). Q&A (15 mins).

We need the **human-in-the-loop** and human verified semantically modelled data to support the AI and current LLMs

But maybe for the next minutes also 🐑 Óghie and 🐿️ Squilly

In the interdisciplinary field of Cultural Heritage, research data is federated in heterogeneous and distributed repositories

label — **Phaistos disc** (Q465338) — item identifier

description — inscribed tablet found in Crete
Phaistos Disk | Phaestos Disc — aliases
▶ In more languages

property — **inception** — value

1700 BCE	value
earliest date 1700 BCE	qualifiers
latest date 1100 BCE	
sourcing circumstances circa	
reason for preferred rank preferred determination method	

rank — ▼ 1 reference — opened reference

stated in	Le pouvoir de l'écrit
author	Louis Godart
page(s)	206

+ add reference

statement group —

property — **location of discovery** — value

1400 BCE	value
end time 1970	
start time 1959	

▶ 1 reference — collapsed reference

+ add value

statement group —

+ add reference

+ add (statement)

Mtrognitz, CCO, via Wikimedia Commons

Integrating community-driven infrastructures such as the Wikiverse and OpenStreetMap is need for a **“real” ground-truth**

This could be done using (community-driven) Wikibase instances

With examples of Cultural Heritage Artefacts, Vulcano Finds and 3D-Data

RDF/LOD

Wikibase

FDO

Irish Ogham Stones

Wikidata
Semantic Kompakkt
FactGrid
fuzzy-sl Wikibase (wikibase.cloud)

Campanian Ignimbrite

fuzzy-sl Wikibase (wikibase.cloud)

Holy Wells

Wikidata

3D Model Metadata-Base

SquirrelBase (wikibase.cloud)

The four community-driven Use Cases within three KG core entities

Ogham Stones

Wikiverse + Wikibases

Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)

image: Florian Thiery CC BY 4.0, created using OpenAI's DALLE

Florian Thiery & Peter Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Ogham! 4.-6. AD, early Medieval, “Primitive Irish”

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OPEN SCIENCE FELLOWS PROGRAM

wmds.org/open-science-fellows

Ogham Stones within the KG Ecosystem

CIIC 81

- UCC Cork Stone Corridor: #4
- OSM Node: 11071361392
- Wikidata: Q130529871

Open Street Map Contributors, ODBL

© OpenStreetMap contributors, Imagery © Mapbox

↑ Florian Thieri, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Knoten: CIIC 81 /
UCC 4 (11071361392)

Version #2

added metadata

Bearbeitet vor 19 Tagen von fthiergeo

Änderungssatz #13909380

Standort: 51.8938126, -8.4921198

Tags

historic	ogham_stone
inscription	C[A]SSITT[A7O]S MAQI MU[CO]I CALLITI
moved	yes
moved_to	Q69379477
name	CIIC 81 / UCC 4
project	ogham.link
source	survey
wikidata	Q106680733

↑ Florian Thieri, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

- *Linked Open Ogham Data*: providing the primary URI
 - http://lod.ogham.link/data/OghamStone_Squirrel_collection
- *fuzzy-sl Wikibase*: coordinates and how they are created
 - [P4](#)
- *Wikidata*: data-hub for external identifiers, e.g., OSM, SMRS, LOD
 - [P11693](#), [P4057](#), [P2888](#)
- *Semantic Kompakt Wikibase*: 3D Model & Annotations
 - [P74](#), [P75](#)
- *FactGrid Wikibase for Historians*: Inscription & Persons & Words
 - [P1219](#), [P33](#), [P256](#)
- Open Street Map
 - [historic=ogham_stone](#)

Use each Resource for data it is “famous” for ...

Define SPARQL query service

```
import os
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from shapely.geometry import Point
import contextily as ctx # For adding OpenStreetMap basemaps
from matplotlib.patches import Patch
from scipy.stats import gaussian_kde
import numpy as np

def querySparql(query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper("https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/api/sparql")
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(JSON)
    results = sparql.queryAndConvert()
    return results['results']['bindings']

# Define the GeoJSON file path
geojson_file = os.path.join(os.getcwd(), "gs_ireland_island.geojson") # Adjusted for ...
```


Define the SPARQL Query

```
# SPARQL Query
oghamQuery = """
PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
?item rdfs:label ?label .
?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
?item oghamonto:within ?c .
?c a oghamonto:County .
?c rdfs:label ?county .
?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
} GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)
"""
```

Visualise the Data as Maps

```
# Filter rows with valid coordinates
df_with_coords = df.dropna(subset=['latitude', 'longitude'])

# Create a GeoDataFrame
gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(
    df_with_coords,
    geometry=[Point(xy) for xy in zip(df_with_coords['longitude'], df_with_coords['latitude'])],
    crs="EPSG:4326"
)

# Convert to Web Mercator for OSM basemap
gdf_mercator = gdf.to_crs(epsg=3857)

# Load Ireland boundary from GeoJSON
ireland_boundary = gpd.read_file(geojson_file)
ireland_boundary = ireland_boundary.to_crs(epsg=3857)
```

Fetch Data and Convert to DataFrame

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(oghamQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []
for result in sparql_results:
    geo = result['geo']['value'] if 'geo' in result else None
    lat, lon = (None, None)
    if geo:
        lon, lat = map(float, geo.replace("POINT(", "").replace(")", "").split())
    data.append({
        "item": result['item']['value'],
        "label": result['label']['value'],
        "county": result['county']['value'],
        "count": int(result.get("count", {}).get("value", 0)),
        "latitude": lat,
        "longitude": lon,
    })

df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df = df.via(https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/jupyter-nb-lod/n40kg-ogham-sites-maps)
```


	item	label	county	count	latitude	longitude
0	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000031	Ballyknock (Ogham Site)	Cork	15	52.026944	-8.071111
1	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000002	Drumlohan (Ogham Site)	Waterford	10	52.163056	-7.468056
2	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000020	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	Kerry	9	52.172500	-10.031111
3	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000149	Kilcoolaght East / Kilhullicaha (Ogham Site)	Kerry	8	52.071944	-9.747222
4	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000170	Knockboy (Ogham Site)	Waterford	8	52.111389	-7.600000
...
191	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000062					
192	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000168					

Map 1: Plot with points coloured by county

```
# Map 1: Plot with points coloured by county
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
unique_counties = gdf['county'].unique()

# Create a colormap with as many colours as unique counties
cmap = plt.get_cmap('tab20', len(unique_counties))
county_colors = {county: cmap(idx) for idx, county in enumerate(unique_counties)}

patches = []
for county, color in county_colors.items():
    county_data = gdf_mercator[gdf_mercator['county'] == county]
    county_data.plot(ax=ax, color=color, markersize=50, alpha=0.7)
    patches.append(Patch(color=color, label=county)) # Add patch for legend

ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties")
plt.legend(handles=patches, title="Counties", bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1), loc='upper left')
plt.show()
```

N40 KG

Item Discussion

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q74)

Ogham Stone #4 UCC Stone Corridor at UCC Cork

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Ogham Stone #4 UCC Stone Corridor at UCC Cork	

Statements

instance of	Archaeological Site	→ 0 references
related to	http://wikidata.org/entity/Q130529671 related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch → 0 references	
related to	https://wikibase.semantic-kompaakt.de/entity/Q1247 related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch → 0 references	
related to	https://database.bartnrd.de/entity/Q1000294 related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch → 0 references	
related to	http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y00000081 related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch → 0 references	

Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

via <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:074>

has coordinate

51°53'37.3"N, 8°29'32.6"W

certainty level	High
certainty description	on-site survey at exhibition area
method used	on-site survey
acting person	Florian Thiery
source type (detail)	on-site survey (source type)
source type (generic)	on-site survey (source type)
method description	on-site survey at UCC Cork
precision	±0.0001°
location type	Exhibition Site
point type	Exhibition
→ 0 references	

51°48'59.58"N, 8°45'57.13"W

certainty level

Low

certainty description

Gippert/Web, Ogham 81:
 "According to Brash, JRSAI 10, 1869, 260, the stone was found in a structure called Rath Lisheenagreine, in the townland of Gurrans (sic!), parish of Templemartin, 1 mile. north of the parish church (the village in question is named "Gurrans" in the Cork U.C. too). A detailed map of the rath (in connection with the larger Rath Lisnacaheragh) is available in S.P. O' R'Yordain's article in PRIA 47-C, 1941-42, 77 ff. - According to Brash, the stone was discovered by one farmer Crowley 17 years before (the publication of his article in JRSAI 10, 1869); Macalister states in CIIC that it "has been known since the sixties" and "appears to have come from a souterrain in the group" of "earth-works" on the townland of Gurrans. The first report was made by John Lyons, C.C., Newcestown, Enniskeane; Brash's visit took place on 16.12.1868. The stone was moved to the Museum of the U.C., Cork after Macalister first visited it (at that time it was still "standing loosely in one of the ditches": CIIC 1, 84). In the collection of the U.C., it is assigned no. 17."

method used

Georeferencing

acting person

Florian Thiery

source type (generic)

Textual Description

source type (detail)

Paper

method description

found in old documents

precision

±0.0001°

location type

Findspot

point type

Location of a Place as a Concept

fuzzy-sl Wikibase [Q74]

Define SPARQL query service

```
import os
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from shapely.geometry import Point
import contextily as ctx # For adding OpenStreetMap basemaps
from matplotlib.patches import Patch
from scipy.stats import gaussian_kde
import numpy as np

def querySparql(query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper("https://query.wikidata.org/sparql")
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(JSON)
    results = sparql.queryAndConvert()
    return results['results']['bindings']

# Define the GeoJSON file path
geojson_file = os.path.join(os.getcwd(), "gs_ireland_island.geojson") # Adjusted for Jupyter
```

Define the SPARQL Query

```
# SPARQL Query
oghamQuery = """
SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?site ?siteLabel ?county ?countyLabel WHERE {
  ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q804647.
  ?item wdt:P189 ?site.
  ?site wdt:P31 wd:Q72617071.
  ?item wdt:P189 ?county.
  ?county wdt:P31 wd:Q759872.
  ?item wdt:P625 ?geo.
  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en." }
}
"""
```

Fetch Data and Convert to DataFrame

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(oghamQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []
for result in sparql_results:
    geo = result['geo']['value'] if 'geo' in result else None
    lat, lon = (None, None)
    if geo:
        lon, lat = map(float, geo.replace("Point(", "").replace(")", "").split(","))
    data.append({
        "item": result['item']['value'],
        "itemLabel": result['itemLabel']['value'],
        "site": result['site']['value'],
        "siteLabel": result['siteLabel']['value'],
        "county": result['county']['value'],
        "countyLabel": result['countyLabel']['value'],
        "latitude": lat,
        "longitude": lon,
    })

df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df
```

Visualise the Data as Maps

```
# Check if DataFrame is populated
if df.empty:
    print("No data retrieved from the query.")
else:
    # Filter rows with valid coordinates
    df_with_coords = df.dropna(subset=['latitude', 'longitude'])

    # Create a GeoDataFrame
    gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(
        df_with_coords,
        geometry=[Point(xy) for xy in zip(df_with_coords['longitude'], df_with_coords['latitude'])],
        crs="EPSG:4326"
    )

    # Convert to Web Mercator for OSM basemap
    gdf_mercator = gdf.to_crs(epsg=3857)

    # Load Ireland boundary from GeoJSON
    ireland_boundary = gpd.read_file(geojson_file)
    ireland_boundary = ireland_boundary.to_crs(epsg=3857)

    # Map 1: Plot points without text decorations
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
    gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, color='red', markersize=50, alpha=0.7, label='ogham sites')
    ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
    ax.set_axis_off()
    plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites (OSM)")
    plt.legend()
    plt.show()

    # Map 2: Plot with points colored by county and fix legend
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
    unique_counties = gdf['countyLabel'].unique()
    colors = plt.cm.tab20.colors[:len(unique_counties)] # Generate unique colors
    county_colors = {county: colors[idx] for idx, county in enumerate(unique_counties)}

    patches = []
    for county, color in county_colors.items():
        county_data = gdf_mercator[gdf_mercator['countyLabel'] == county]
        county_data.plot(ax=ax, color=color, markersize=50, alpha=0.7)
        patches.append(Patch(color=color, label=county)) # Add patch for legend

    ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
    ax.set_axis_off()
    plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties")
    plt.legend(handles=patches, title="Counties", bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1), loc='upper left')
    plt.show()

    # Map 3: Density map with normalized values
    x = gdf_mercator.geometry.x
    y = gdf_mercator.geometry.y

    # Calculate kernel density
    xy = np.vstack([x, y])
    kde = gaussian_kde(xy)
    density = kde(xy)

    # Normalize density to range [0, 1]
    density_normalized = (density - density.min()) / (density.max() - density.min())
    gdf_mercator['density'] = density_normalized

    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
    ireland_boundary.plot(ax=ax, color="white", edgecolor="black")
    gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, column='density', cmap="Reds", markersize=50, alpha=0.7, legend=True)
    ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
    ax.set_axis_off()
    plt.title("Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)")
    plt.show()
```


	item	itemLabel	site	siteLabel	county	countyLabel	latitude	longitude
0	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892459	CIIC 71 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85394002	Ahalisky (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.678889	-8.846944
1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892460	CIIC 72 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85394004	Aultagh (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.770833	-9.088056
2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892463	CIIC 73 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393926	Carhoovauler (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.688333	-8.956111
3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892466	CIIC 74 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393926	Carhoovauler (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.688333	-8.956111
4	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892468	CIIC 75 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393928	Keenrath (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.759444	-9.185833
...
328	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892620	CIIC 156 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
329	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892623	CIIC 157 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
330	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892626	CIIC 158 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
331	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892629	CIIC 159 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
332	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892630	CIIC 160 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111

333 rows x 8 columns

via <https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/jupyter-nb-lod/wikidata-ogham-sites-map>

Wikidata

Map of Ogham Stone Sites (OSM)

(C) OpenStreetMap contributors

Item Discussion

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q130529871)

Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

CIC 81

In more languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor	CIC 81
German	No label defined	No description defined	
French	No label defined	No description defined	
Bavarian	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

Instance of

- ogham stone 0 references
- Ogham Stone Semantic Concept 0 references
- archaeological artifact 0 references

Identifiers

FactGrid item ID Q1000294 0 references

Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID CO074-148---- 0 references

OpenStreetMap node ID 11071361392 0 references

Wikidata [Q130529871]

Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)

Item Discussion

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q1247)

3D model of the Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

edit

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	3D model of the Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor	
British English	No label defined	No description defined	

► Mapping to other ontologies

Predicate	URL	
		+ add mapping

Statements

instance of	Media item	edit
	▼ 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

license	Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike	edit
	▼ 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

has technique	Photogrammetry	edit
---------------	----------------	------

file view

<https://semantic-kompakkt.de/entity/670e54210da6ec51ee08e5fb>

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV

3D model of the Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

Related agents

Rightsowner: [University College Cork \(UCC\)](#)

Data Creator: [Anne-Karoline Distel](#)

Creator: [Anne-Karoline Distel](#)

Editor: [Florian Thierj](#)

Contact Person: [Florian Thierj](#)

Licence

[Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International \(CC BY-NC-SA 4.0\)](#)

Creation

Technique: [Photogrammetry](#)

Software: [KIRI engine](#)

Equipment: Smartphone

Date: Invalid Date

Related object structure

[Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV](#)

cassittas (Q1013406)

a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	cassittas	a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

Item Discussion

C[A]SSITT[A]S Annotation (CIIC 81) (Q1255)

Person in C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUQOI CALLITI

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	C[A]SSITT[A]S Annotation (CIIC 81)	Person in C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUQOI CALLITI

Main page
Recent changes
Random page
Help about MediaWiki

Wikibase
New item

Semantic Kompakt [Q1247]

via <https://database.factorid.de/wiki/Item:Q1000294>

Main page
Query service
Sample queries
Advanced text search
Recent changes

Browse
FactGrid Viewer
Knowledge Browser
EntiTree genealogies

Project Spaces
Blog
Projects historically
Projects alphabetically
Projects personally
To Do
SPARQL Lab

Items & Properties
New Item
MergeItems
Batch fragments
QuickStatements
Directory of Properties
New Property
Data modeling
Help

Lexemes
New Lexeme
Search

Tools
What links here
Related changes
Special pages
Printable version
Permanent link
Page information
Concept URI

Item Discussion

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q1000294)

Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

▼ In more languages

Language	Label	Description
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor
British English	No label defined	No description defined

Statements

Instance of	Ogham Stone	▼ 0 references
Research projects that contributed to this data set	The FactGrid Ogham Project (2024-)	▼ 0 references
Language	Ogham	▼ 0 references
Genre classification	Ogham Stone	▼ 0 references
Script style	Ogham	▼ 0 references

inscription

C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUCCI CALLITI

▼ 0 references

Persons mentioned

cassittas

▼ 0 references

Calliti

▼ 0 references

Things mentioned

MAQI

▼ 0 references

MUCCI

▼ 0 references

cassittas (Q1013406)

a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	cassittas	a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

Calliti (Q1013407)

a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Ston

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	Calliti	a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Ston

MAQI (Q1013408)

son

MAQ | MAC | /-#- | MACCI | MAQI | MACV | MACI

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	MAQI	son	MAQ MAC /-#- MACCI MAQI MACV MACI

MUCCI (Q1013410)

túath, tribe

/-#- | MACCU | MOCU | MOCCI | MOCO

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	MUCCI	túath, tribe	/-#- MACCU MOCU MOCCI MOCO

FactGrid [Q1000294]

overpass turbo

```

1 /*
2 This is an example Overpass query.
3 Try it out by pressing the Run button above!
4 You can find more examples with the Load tool.
5 */
6 node
7 [historic=ogham_stone]
8 {{{bbox}}};
9 out;

```

```

<node id="5145413640" lat="52.1102476" lon="-10.4731913">
  <tag k="historic" v="ogham_stone"/>
  <tag k="inscription" v="ERC MAQI MAQI-ERCIAS MU DOVINIA"/>
  <tag k="moved" v="no"/>
  <tag k="name" v="CIIC 178"/>
  <tag k="project" v="ogham.link"/>
  <tag k="ref:IE:smr" v="KE052-059002-"/>
  <tag k="source" v="survey"/>
  <tag k="wikidata" v="Q70892682"/>
  <tag k="wikimedia_commons" v="File:Coumeenoole_Ogham_Stone_(Dunmore_Head).jpg"/>
</node>

```

Node 5145413640

Tags

- historic = ogham_stone
- inscription = ERC MAQI MAQI-ERCIAS MU DOVINIA
- moved = no
- name = CIIC 178
- project = ogham.link
- ref:IE:smr = KE052-059002-
- source = survey
- wikidata = Q70892682
- wikimedia_commons = File:Coumeenoole_Ogham_Stone_(Dunmore_Head).jpg
- PE

Coordinates:
52.1102476 / -10.4731913 (latlon)

geladen – Nodes: 7, Ways: 0, Relations: 0
angezeigt – POIs: 7, Linien: 0, Polygone: 0

Leaflet | © OpenStreetMap contributors
geladen – Nodes: 106, Ways: 0, Relations: 0
angezeigt – POIs: 106, Linien: 0, Polygone: 0

via <https://overpass-turbo.eu/s/1lwq>

Florian Thierry, CC BY 4.0, via [Wikimedia Commons](#)

OpenStreetMap [Overpass-Turbo]

Federating between *Semantic Kompakt* to get the 3D file view location & *Wikidata* to get all external IDs

Wikibase / Query Service Examples

Query Helper

+ Filter

object of representation

+ Show

file view

wikidata id

Limit

[Query source](#)

```

1 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wdt: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX wdqs: <https://query.wikidata.org/sparql>
4
5 SELECT DISTINCT ?CIIC81Label ?3D_view ?wd_id ?OSM_id ?SMRS_id ?LOD_id ?Factgrid_id WHERE {
6   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
7   VALUES ?CIIC81 {tib:Q1407}
8   ?Media_item tibt:P63 ?CIIC81.
9   ?Media_item tibt:P74 ?3D_view.
10  ?CIIC81 tibt:P107 ?wd_id.
11
12  BIND(IRI(CONCAT(STR(wd:), ?wd_id)) AS ?wd_item)
13
14  SERVICE wdqs: {
15    ?wd_item wdt:P11693 ?OSM_id;
16    wdt:P4057 ?SMRS_id;
17    wdt:P2888 ?LOD_id;
18    wdt:P8168 ?Factgrid_id.
19  }
20 }
21

```


1 result in 513 ms

CIIC81Label	3D_view	wd_id	OSM_id	SMRS_id	LOD_id	Factgrid_id
Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	https://semantic-kompakt.de/entity/670e542110da6ec51ee08e5fb	Q130529871	11071361392	CO074-148----	http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081	Q1000294

Federating between Wikidata (to get external IDs), FactGrid (to get related people and inscriptions), and Fuzzy Spatial Locations (fuzzy-sl) to get coordinates*

*NB: Not possible to ask full questions though, due to limited SPARQL functionalities

```

1 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wdt: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
4 PREFIX fslwd: <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/entity/>
5 PREFIX fslwdt: <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/prop/direct/>
6 PREFIX fgt: <https://database.factgrid.de/entity/>
7 PREFIX fgt: <https://database.factgrid.de/prop/direct/>
8
9 SELECT ?label ?wikiq ?factgridq ?fslq ?inscription ?related_personsLabels ?coordinates ?osmnode ?smrid ?uri WHERE {
10 SERVICE <https://query.wikidata.org/sparql> {
11   ?wikiq wdt:P31 wd:Q2016147.
12   FILTER(?wikiq = wd:Q130529871)
13   ?wikiq rdfs:label ?label.
14   FILTER(LANG(?label) IN("en"))
15   ?wikiq wdt:P8168 ?factgridq;
16   wdt:P11693 ?osmnode;
17   wdt:P4057 ?smrid;
18   wdt:P2888 ?uri.
19 }
20 SERVICE <https://database.factgrid.de/sparql> {
21   fgt:Q1000294 fgt:P1219 ?inscription;
22   fgt:P33 ?related_persons;
23   fgt:P1215 ?fslq.
24   ?related_persons rdfs:label ?related_personsLabels.
25   FILTER(LANG(?related_personsLabels) IN("en"))
26 }
27 SERVICE <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/query/sparql> { fslwd:Q74 fslwdt:P4 ?coordinates. }
28 }
    
```

<https://sparql.dblp.org/YKlrP3>

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

Query results: 2 lines found | 11ms in total | 11ms for computation | 0.0ms for resolving and sending

	?label	?wikiq	?factgridq	?fslq	?inscription	?related_personsLabels	?coordinates	?osmnode	?smrid	?uri
1	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Q130529871	Q1000294	Q74	C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUCOI CALLITI	casstias	Point(-8.492443111 51.893659305)	11071361392	CO074- 148----	Y50000081
2	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Q130529871	Q1000294	Q74	C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUCOI CALLITI	Calliti	Point(-8.492443111 51.893659305)	11071361392	CO074- 148----	Y50000081

Federating between *Semantic Kompakkt* (as starting point), *Wikidata* (to get external IDs), *FactGrid* (to get Fuzzy-SL ID), and *Fuzzy Spatial Locations* (*fuzzy-sl*) to get coordinates*

*NB: Not possible out of the box – requires additional config of the allowlist & relatively complex syntax, prone to mistakes when writing manually

[Query source](#)

```
Wikibase / Query Service Examples
1 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wdt: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX wdqs: <https://query.wikidata.org/sparql>
4 PREFIX fslwd: <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/entity/>
5 PREFIX fslwdt: <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/prop/direct/>
6 PREFIX fg: <https://database.factgrid.de/entity/>
7 PREFIX fgt: <https://database.factgrid.de/prop/direct/>
8
9 SELECT DISTINCT ?CIIC81Label ?3D_view ?wd_id ?OSM_id ?SMRS_id ?LOD_id
10 ?Factgrid_id ?fuzzy_id ?coordinates WHERE {
11 SERVICE wikibase:label {
12 bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
13 VALUES ?CIIC81 {tib:Q1407}
14 ?Media_item tib:P63 ?CIIC81.
15 ?Media_item tib:P74 ?3D_view.
16 ?CIIC81 tib:P107 ?wd_id.
17
18 BIND(IRI(CONCAT(STR(wd:), ?wd_id)) AS ?wd_item)
19
20 SERVICE wdqs: {
21 ?wd_item wdt:P11693 ?OSM_id;
22 wdt:P4057 ?SMRS_id;
23 wdt:P2888 ?LOD_id;
24 wdt:P8168 ?Factgrid_id.
25 }
26
27 BIND(IRI(CONCAT(STR(fg:), ?Factgrid_id)) AS ?Factgrid_item)
28 SERVICE <https://database.factgrid.de/sparql> {
29 ?Factgrid_item fgt:P1215 ?fuzzy_id.
30 }
31
32 BIND(IRI(CONCAT(STR(fslwd:), ?fuzzy_id)) AS ?fuzzy_item)
33 SERVICE <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/query/sparql> {
34 ?fuzzy_item fslwdt:P4 ?coordinates.
35 }
36 }
37
```

1 result in 520 ms

CIIC81Label	3D_view	wd_id	OSM_id	SMRS_id	LOD_id	Factgrid_id	fuzzy_id	coordinates
Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	<https://semantic-kompakkt.de/entity/670e54210da6ec51ee08e5fb>	Q130529871	11071361392	CO074-148---	<http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081>	Q1000294	Q74	Point(-8.492443111 51.893659305)

Holy Wells

Wikidata

via <https://wiki/AQ2F>

via <https://wiki/AQ2F>

via https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiProject_HolyWells

Wikidata:WikiProject Holy Wells

Holy Wells in Ireland

ID	Name	Example	Example
Q1111111	St. Ludo's Well	St. Ludo's Well, County Wick	St. Ludo's Well, County Wick
Q1111112	St. Ludo's Well	St. Ludo's Well, County Wick	St. Ludo's Well, County Wick
Q1111113	St. Ludo's Well	St. Ludo's Well, County Wick	St. Ludo's Well, County Wick
Q1111114	St. Ludo's Well	St. Ludo's Well, County Wick	St. Ludo's Well, County Wick
Q1111115	St. Ludo's Well	St. Ludo's Well, County Wick	St. Ludo's Well, County Wick
Q1111116	St. Ludo's Well	St. Ludo's Well, County Wick	St. Ludo's Well, County Wick
Q1111117	St. Ludo's Well	St. Ludo's Well, County Wick	St. Ludo's Well, County Wick
Q1111118	St. Ludo's Well	St. Ludo's Well, County Wick	St. Ludo's Well, County Wick
Q1111119	St. Ludo's Well	St. Ludo's Well, County Wick	St. Ludo's Well, County Wick
Q1111120	St. Ludo's Well	St. Ludo's Well, County Wick	St. Ludo's Well, County Wick

The Citizen Science Wikidata Project Holy Wells

Table - 🔍 25 Ergebnisse in 1876 ms </> Code 📄 Herunter

item	ItemLabel	img	geo	osm	ed
Q:121842432	Saint Fiachra's Well		Point(-7.1978959 52.6216672)	8515265450	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/sheastown-st-fiachres-well-low-poly-be3bcd3a3204744a33b2255465028b8 >
Q:126448724	Our Lady's Well		Point(-7.4730101 52.7209032)	8517818852	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/clomantagh-lobermurry-02f47554c604a8b8665ea1bc00f9fd >
Q:126649228	Lacken Well		Point(-7.2775479 52.5438145)	9886802295	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/garrynamann-lower-lacken-well-d5beb9cc7adb4b248c1bb6c2ec542582 >
Q:126487120	St Coleman's Well		Point(-7.2869104 52.7352502)	998532219	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/jenkinson-st-colmans-well-low-poly-fae5988530c648aea73cfd09663954a0 >
Q:122258894	Saint Fiacre's Well		Point(-6.9330041 52.5808599)	8512180854	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/ullard-st-fiachras-well-low-poly-635f7f9e64b434a6ea08672629b493d >
Q:122304309	Saint Molin's Well (Mullennakill)		Point(-7.11584 52.4307541)	8526433151	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/st-molings-well-low-poly-dcfff49b2f3d4348d5cade4f869ad33 >
Q:126456441	Columbkille's Well		Point(-7.0681791 52.4892388)	8513597500	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/inistioge-st-columbkills-well-low-poly-b0845424e49d40cfa4f0437c98ac7f5 >
Q:126454844	Lady's Well		Point(-6.9566958 52.5411618)	8513574146	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/grauguenamanagh-ladys-well-9ed7bcf22e184897a5b8e758cf7249e >
Q:114439798	Kenny's Well		Point(-7.26219 52.65325)	1158290017	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/kennys-well-indoors-low-poly-685c7b9d3b0e4ba09e22263342cfc3 >
Q:126458702	St. Nicholas's Well (Killamery)		Point(-7.4459883 52.4752746)	6167966637	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/killamery-st-nicholas-well-low-poly-0eeb400854164819afc5bae58dff8da >
Q:126456487	Well of the Festival		Point(-7.1257749 52.4660232)	8518908237	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/powerswood-tobernaliha-ee33390870b4d9886a0bb3c42029df69 >
Q:126456487	Well of the Festival		Point(-7.1257749 52.4660232)	8518908237	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/powerswood-tobernaliha-ee33390870b4d9886a0bb3c42029df69 >
Q:129263926	Holy Well		Point(-7.1637296 52.5134682)	7673751375	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/newtown-jeipoint-st-nicholas-well-62521654a1ec40c7430ccbf448869 >
Q:126374490	Trinity Well		Point(-7.2710769 52.7262158)	11942593399	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/ballyraffon-trinity-well-553073f9100040e789890d3edd3cd851 >
Q:122302608	St. Kieran's Well		Point(-7.3800887 52.3975027)	10544065862	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/whitechurch-kilkieran-st-kierans-well-8cdea3b21314508eb7b69faca418d76 >
Q:121840779	St. Lachtain's Well		Point(-7.38951 52.7316)		< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/freshford-st-lachtains-well-low-poly-ae1ef14d4aa7d433bbf076407134e81e >
Q:122258906	Lady's Well		Point(-7.0093773 52.6293381)	8513439301	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/goresbridge-ladys-well-statue-low-poly-6bdcfdcece3e4f6ab15a3ad6550c2d18 >
Q:122258906	Lady's Well		Point(-7.0093773 52.6293381)	8513439301	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/goresbridge-ladys-well-statue-low-poly-6bdcfdcece3e4f6ab15a3ad6550c2d18 >
Q:122258906	Lady's Well		Point(-7.0093773 52.6293381)	8513439301	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/goresbridge-ladys-well-statue-low-poly-6bdcfdcece3e4f6ab15a3ad6550c2d18 >
Q:122189562	Saint Augustine's Well		Point(-7.38765 52.54522)		< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/callan-st-augustines-well-low-poly-9feacac0fa14a189a1a59d2e123b1e4 >
Q:126456468	Holy Cross well		Point(-7.0437511 52.4878257)	8513475323	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/kilcross-holy-cross-well-low-poly-ca165580c28429392b1a06491333148 >
Q:126657210	St. David's Well		Point(-7.2979334 52.6195581)	12144739129	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/castleinch-st-davids-well-4b6eae78a6cc43c2ae79bb6ab7c69a8 >
Q:126918993	Kilkeasy Holy Well		Point(-7.2246427 52.4410735)	12015630647	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/kilkeasy-holy-well-67a39daeb3c54539a8a3147eb29f3f67 >
Q:126487358	St Brigid's Well		Point(-7.3565632 52.6115585)	8517798092	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/toberbreedia-st-brigids-well-56e71b0735fc4f17bdf3e4c5b2a12a7 >
Q:126454422	St Leonard's Well		Point(-7.2955635 52.5006254)	7412516778	< https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/st-leonards-well-c6e89f2e2ae147ba90553a3a16fda690 >

Holy Wells having Sketchfab Links to 3D-Models

b-unicycling, CC BY 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/oWvIB>

Anne-Karoline Distel, CC0, via Wikimedia Commons

Freshford: St Lachtain's Well

via <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q121840779>

Wikidata

Toberlachtain (Q121840779)

Holy well dedicated to St. Lachtain near Freshford, Co. Kildare

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Toberlachtain	Holy well dedicated to St. Lachtain near Freshford, Co. Kildare	Tober Lachtain St. Lachtain's Well Toberlaghtain
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Russian	No label defined	No description defined	
Arabic	No label defined	No description defined	
Arabic	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

- instance of: **holy well** (1 reference)
- Holy Well Semantic Concept (0 references)
- spring (3 references)
- holy well (1 reference)
- date of last update to list: 1929 (1 reference)

Identifiers

- Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID**: KK013-025---- (1 reference)
- OpenStreetMap way ID**: 935503837 (0 references)

OpenStreetMap | Bearbeiten | Chronik | Export

Suchen:

Weg: Saint Lachtain's Well (935503837)
Version #7
added sketchfab link

Bearbeitet vor 3 Monaten von bruncycling
Änderungssatz #15259797

Tags

alt_name	Toberlachtain
amenity	place_of_worship
check_date	2023-08-25
denomination	roman_catholic
description	Walled enclosure with wrought iron gate. Stone paved ground with subterranean water basin which is covered in water lenses.
name	Toberlaghtain
name:en	Saint Lachtain's Well
name:etymological:en	Q18674069
name:ga	Tober Lachtain
natural	spring
place_of_worship	holy_well
ref:en:en	KK013-025
religion	christian
source	British War Office mapsurvey

via <https://www.openstreetmap.org/way/935503837>

Freshford: St Lachtain's Well

Campanian Ignimbrite

fuzzy-sl Wikibase (wikibase.cloud)

The huge question on uncertainty and ambiguities ...

fuzzy-sl Wikibase Modelling Scheme

About 40'000 yr b2k ago, the largest eruption of the Campanian Ignimbrite (CI) took place in the Phlegraean Fields.

These sites are recorded in several publications, e.g. with coordinates or references to cities, regions, caves and archaeological sites.

Fitzsimmons et al. (2014), p.76

“In this paper we investigate [...] the site of Urluia Quarry on the Dobrogea loess plateau [...], **some 15 km south of the Danube River**. The site immediately overlies the Quaternary-uplifted Cretaceous-Tertiary-age limestone basement rocks (Munteanu et al., 2008), which were the target of earlier quarrying activities.”

Pötter et al. (2021), p.5

“The Urluia (URL) LPS is **located in an abandoned limestone quarry on the limestone plateau of the Dobrogea** (Fitzsimmons et al., 2013; Fitzsimmons and Hambach, 2014; Obrecht et al., 2017).”

Where is Urluia / Romania?

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

http://fizzy-squirrel.link/data/cisite_52

Property	Value
containsArea (list contains:Desc)	Indopot mentioned in a scientific paper (ref langString) (66391 en)
containsLevel (list contains:Level)	medium (list medium) [x]
hasReference (list hasReference)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fitzsimmons et al., 2014, 2013 (void string) Obadă et al., 2017 (void string) Pfeifer et al., 2021 (void string)
partOf (list partOf)	CampianingămbraProject (list CampianingămbraProject) [x]
siteType (list siteType)	ArchaeologicalSite (list ArchaeologicalSite) [x]
spatialType (list spatialType)	InhabitedPlace (list InhabitedPlace) [x]
hasCoordinates (list hasCoordinates)	clisite_52_geom (list clisite_52_geom)
type (list type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity (prov Entity) [x] Place (places Places) [x]
comment (list comment)	Cl findspot related from literature (ref langString) (66391 en)
label (list label)	Urluia (Romania) (ref langString) (66391 en)
closeMatch (list closeMatch)	664132 (list closeMatch) [x]
prefLabel (list prefLabel)	Urluia (Romania) (ref langString) (66391 en)
scopeNote (list scopeNote)	Cl findspot related from literature (ref langString) (66391 en)
isMember (list member) of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity Instances Collection (list Entity_instances_collection) Place Instances Collection (list Place_instances_collection) Site Instances Collection (list Site_instances_collection)
is used (prov:used) of	clisite_52_activity (list clisite_52_activity)

CLC:code	131
CLC:explanation	See http://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Romania_CLC_import .
CLC:shapeld	6840
CLC:year	2006
landuse	quarry
source	European Environment Agency (EEA), CORINE Land Cover, 2006
source:ro	Agenția Europeană de Mediu, CORINE Land Cover, 2006

<http://www.openstreetmap.org/way/84975654>

The location coordinates can be determined approximately

Main page
Recent changes
Random page
Help about MediaWiki

Tools
What links here
Related changes
Special pages
Printable version
Permanent link
Page information
Concept URI

Wikibase
New Item
New Property
New Schema
All Properties
Query Service
Cradle
QuickStatements

In other languages
Add links

Item Discussion

Urluia Quarry (Q73)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot

> In more languages
cotqum

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Urluia Quarry	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot	
German	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

instance of	Geological Site
	0 references

via <https://doi.org/10.3390/quat2020017>, Fig. 1

has reference	Fitzsimmons et al., 2014	0 references
	Fitzsimmons et al., 2013	0 references
	Obreht et al., 2017	0 references
	Pötter et al., 2021	0 references

related to	http://openstreetmap.org/way/84975654	0 references
	http://sws.geonames.org/664132	0 references
	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q13054772	0 references

has coordinate

44°5'40.9"N, 27°54'17.6"E

certainty level Medium

certainty description Fitzsimmons et al. (2014), p.76: "In this paper we investigate [...] the site of Urluia Quarry on the Dobrogea loess plateau [...], some 15 km south of the Danube River. The site immediately overlies the Quaternary-uplifted Cretaceous-Tertiary-age limestone basement rocks (Munteanu et al., 2008), which were the target of earlier quarrying activities."; Pötter et al. (2021), p.5: "The Urluia (URL) LPS is located in an abandoned limestone quarry on the limestone plateau of the Dobrogea (Fitzsimmons et al., 2013; Fitzsimmons and Hambach, 2014; Obreht et al., 2017)."

method used Georeferencing

acting person Fiona Schenk

source type (detail) Paper

source type (generic) Textual Description

method description set a point based on Fitzsimmons et al. (2014), p.76 and Pötter et al. (2021), p.5 using OSM Way 84975654

precision ±0.0001°

location type Findspot

point type Location of a Place as a Concept

1 reference

reference (String) Fitzsimmons et al. (2014), p.76

Pötter et al. (2021), p.5

Urluia @ fuzzy-sl Wikibase [Q73]

3D Model Metadata-Base

SquirrelBase (wikibase.cloud)

<https://squirrelbase.wikibase.cloud>

3D objects are citable via the **squirrelbase Wikibase**

“138 Adlersteine markierten als mittelalterliche Grenzsteine einst die Grenzen des Aachener Reichs. Von denen sind maximal noch 18 Steine zu finden, manche demoliert und unleserlich.” Quelle: Wikimedia Commons (<https://w.wiki/AmoM>)

Adlerstein (“eagle stone”)

Wikidata navigation menu including: Main page, Community portal, Project chat, Create a new item, Recent changes, Random item, Query Service, Nearby, Help, Donate, Levensgeografisch data, Create a new Levensre, Recent changes, Random Levensre, Tools, What links here, Related changes, Special pages, Permanent link, Page information, Concept URI, Cite this page, Get structured LRI, Download QR code.

Item Discussion

Boundary stone with eagle (Q17445038)

monument in Vaals, Netherlands ✎ edit

→ In more languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Boundary stone with eagle	monument in Vaals, Netherlands	
German	Adlerstein Grenzstein (Aachen)	Vaals, Netherlands	Adlerstein am Vaalser Berg (So...
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

instance of ✎ boundary marker ✎ edit

- 0 references + add reference

✎ monolith ✎ edit

- 0 references + add reference

+ add value

image ✎ edit

Vaals-Grenssteen achter Wilhelmintoren (1).JPG
3,000 × 4,000, 4.11 MB

point in time 22 November 2010

- 0 references + add reference

+ add value

country ✎ Netherlands ✎ edit

- 0 references + add reference

+ add value

located in the administrative territorial entity ✎ Vaals ✎ edit

- 0 references + add reference

+ add value

located on street ✎ Vargrenzeberg ✎ edit

- 0 references + add reference

+ add value

location ✎ Vaals ✎ edit

- 0 references + add reference

+ add value

located in/on physical feature ✎ Vaalserberg ✎ edit

- 0 references + add reference

+ add value

coordinate location ✎ ✎ edit

- 0 references + add reference

+ add value

heritage designation ✎ Rijksmonument ✎ edit

start time 23 January 1907

+ 1 reference + add reference

+ add value

street address ✎ aan de NL-DE-grens achter de Wilhelmintoren op de Vaalserberg ✎ edit

(Dutch)

- 0 references + add reference

+ add value

Commons category ✎ Grenssteen achter Wilhelmintoren, Vaals ✎ edit

+ 0 references + add reference

+ add value

+ add statement

Identifiers

Rijksmonument ID ✎ 30638 ✎ edit

+ 0 references + add reference

+ add value

OpenStreetMap node ID ✎ 112850400 ✎ edit

+ 0 references + add reference

+ add value

Adlerstein in Vaals (Netherlands) in Wikidata

Adlerstein in Vaals (Netherlands) in Sketchfab / 3DHOP

Adlerstein in Vaals (Niederlande) (Q5)

object

in more languages

Statements

instance of	Object	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
KIRI URL	https://www.kiriengine.app/share/ShareMode?code=Q7ZG14&size=doc&715ba51441988848b71f7bb0562	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
Wikidata Q-ID	Q17445038	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
OSM ID	node/1128569466	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
geometry	50°45'42.2276"N, 6°17.4392"E	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
3DCHIP URL	http://archaeosquirrelis.cloud/?mode=NLRMR-36038	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
Skiatcheo URL	https://skitchfab.com/3d-mode/adlerstein-grenzstein-in-aachen-ca827c32825c44f9ba1f6ca178e5519b	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

Sidebar:

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- Add links

Adlerstein in Vaals (Netherlands) Q5

Snow Man in St. Magdalena (Gsies)

Item [Discussion](#)

Schneemann in St. Magdalena (Gsies) (Q18)

temporal object edit

[In more languages](#)

Statements

instance of

temporal Object edit

[0 references](#)

[+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

KIRI URL

<https://www.kiriengine.app/share/ShareModel?code=G7ZGI4&serialize=f784a11993b745669f5d73685c7685f8> edit

[0 references](#)

[+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

geometry

[46°51'8.294"N, 12°14'53.135"E](#) edit

[0 references](#)

[+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

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- [Add links](#)

Snow Man in St. Magdalena (Gsies) **Q18**

 KIRI Engine

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Ice-Cairn at Pragser Wildsee

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Wikibase
New Item
New Property
New Schema
All Properties
Query Service
Cradle
QuickStatements

In other languages
Add links

Item Discussion

Eismännchen auf Stein auf dem Pragser Wildsee (Q21)

temporal object

edit

[In more languages](#)

Statements

instance of	temporal Object	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

KIRI URL	https://www.kiriengine.app/share/ShareModel?code=G7ZG4&serialize=ae53941ea80744668b8fe9dd133a745b	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

OSM ID	relation/14517899	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

Wikidata Q-ID	Q445369	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

geometry	46°41'48.1114"N, 12°5'1.7318"E	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

Ice-Cairn at Pragser Wildsee **Q21**

Jupyter Python Minions for OG(H)AM

*Implementing the FAIR4RS principles
using Wikibase Instances*

image created using Google's Gemini

Use Research Software Engineering techniques for the FAIRification of (Wikibase) Data, maybe using Python and Jupyter Notebooks

Define SPARQL query service

```
import os
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from shapely.geometry import Point
import contextily as ctx # For adding OpenStreetMap basemaps
from matplotlib.patches import Patch
from scipy.stats import gaussian_kde
import numpy as np

def querySparql(query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper("https://query.wikidata.org/sparql")
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(JSON)
    results = sparql.queryAndConvert()
    return results['results']['bindings']

# Define the GeoJSON file path
geojson_file = os.path.join(os.getcwd(), "gs_ireland_island_geojson") # Adjusted for Jupyter Notebook
```

Define the SPARQL Query

```
# SPARQL Query
oghamQuery = """
SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?site ?siteLabel ?county ?countyLabel WHERE {
    ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q8016167.
    ?item wdt:P189 ?site.
    ?site wdt:P31 wd:Q72617071.
    ?item wdt:P189 ?county.
    ?county wdt:P31 wd:Q179872.
    ?item wdt:P625 ?geo.
    SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en" . }
}
"""
```

Fetch Data and Convert to DataFrame

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(oghamQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []

for result in sparql_results:
    geo = result['geo']['value'] if 'geo' in result else None
    lat, lon = (None, None)
    if geo:
        lon, lat = map(float, geo.replace("Point(", "").replace(")", "").split())
        data.append({
            "item": result['item']['value'],
            "itemLabel": result['itemLabel']['value'],
            "site": result['site']['value'],
            "siteLabel": result['siteLabel']['value'],
            "county": result['county']['value'],
            "countyLabel": result['countyLabel']['value'],
            "latitude": lat,
            "longitude": lon,
        })

df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df
```

	item	itemLabel	site	siteLabel	county	countyLabel	latitude	longitude
0	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892459	CIIC 71 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85394002	Ahalisky (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.678889	-8.846944
1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892460	CIIC 72 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85394004	Aultagh (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.770833	-9.088056
2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892463	CIIC 73 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393926	Carhoovauler (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.688333	-8.956111
3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892466	CIIC 74 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393926	Carhoovauler (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.688333	-8.956111
4	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892468	CIIC 75 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393928	Keenrath (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.759444	-9.185833
...
328	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892620	CIIC 156 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
329	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892623	CIIC 157 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
330	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892626	CIIC 158 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
331	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892629	CIIC 159 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
332	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892630	CIIC 160 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111

333 rows × 8 columns

<https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/jupyter-nb-lod/wikidata-ogham-sites-map>

SPARQL query to create a DataFrame

Visualise the Data as Maps

```
# Check if DataFrame is populated
if df.empty:
    print("No data retrieved from the query.")
else:
    # Filter rows with valid coordinates
    df_with_coords = df.dropna(subset=['latitude', 'longitude'])

    # Create a GeoDataFrame
    gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(
        df_with_coords,
        geometry=[Point(xy) for xy in zip(df_with_coords['longitude'], df_with_coords['latitude'])],
        crs="EPSG:4326"
    )

    # Convert to Web Mercator for OSM basemap
    gdf_mercator = gdf.to_crs(eps=3857)

    # Load Ireland boundary from GeoJSON
    ireland_boundary = gpd.read_file(geojson_file)
    ireland_boundary = ireland_boundary.to_crs(eps=3857)

    # Map 1: Plot points without text decorations
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
    gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, color='red', markersize=50, alpha=0.7, label="Ogham Stones")
    ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
    ax.set_axis_off()
    plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites (OSM)")
    plt.legend()
    plt.show()
```



```
# Map 2: Plot with points colored by county and fix Legend
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
unique_counties = gdf['countyLabel'].unique()
colors = plt.cm.tab20.colors[:len(unique_counties)] # Generate unique colors
county_colors = {county: colors[idx] for idx, county in enumerate(unique_counties)}

patches = []
for county, color in county_colors.items():
    county_data = gdf_mercator[gdf_mercator['countyLabel'] == county]
    county_data.plot(ax=ax, color=color, markersize=50, alpha=0.7)
    patches.append(Patch(color=color, label=county)) # Add patch for Legend

ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties")
plt.legend(handles=patches, title="Counties", bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1), loc='upper left')
plt.show()

# Map 3: Density map with normalized values
x = gdf_mercator.geometry.x
y = gdf_mercator.geometry.y

# Calculate kernel density
xy = np.vstack([x, y])
kde = gaussian_kde(xy)
density = kde(xy)

# Normalize density to range [0, 1]
density_normalized = (density - density.min()) / (density.max() - density.min())
gdf_mercator['density'] = density_normalized

fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
ireland_boundary.plot(ax=ax, color="white", edgecolor="black")
gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, column='density', cmap="Reds", markersize=50, alpha=0.7, legend=True)
ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)")
plt.show()
```

Source Code to create maps

Map of Ogham Stone Sites (OSM)

Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties

- Counties
- County Cork
- County Limerick
- County Donegal
- County Mayo
- County Kildare
- County Kerry
- County Galway
- County Leitrim
- County Roscommon
- County Waterford
- County Wexford
- County Cavan
- County Carlow
- County Kilkenny
- County Louth
- County Meath
- County Wicklow
- County Clare

Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)

The Map output with OSM base layer

Add-On from yesterday...

Govan Stones

Semantic Kompakkt

6.2 Govan 2

The hogbacks of Govan have been the subject of intense study since James Lang's original consideration of the Scottish hogbacks (1974); scholarly interest in this monument type has only increased since (Lang 1984; Lang 1994; Ritchie 2004; Crawford 2005; Williams 2015; Whitworth 2016; Barnes 2019). Govan 2 (Lang 1, ECMS 2), is one of the best preserved of the Govan hogbacks. A band of a variety of median-incised motifs has been carved along the bottom of the monument; while the art historical similarities with the Irish sea and Cumbria have been considered in previous discussion of these motifs (Lang 1994, 125), but it is also worth noting that the ring-chain utilised in the band is very similar to that found elsewhere in the Govan collection on Govan 24 (see Section 6.16 below). Above this band, two rows of concave tiles have been carved on each side. A small panel survives on one of the short edges of the monument, which has been decorated with a swastika motif. Two small panels of step pattern flank this panel. Two weathered beast heads remain, one on each short face of the monument. The ridge of Govan 2, however, is significantly worn. The digital three-dimensional model of the stone revealed that at least one side of the ridge had been previously decorated with step pattern, which has not been commented on previously (Figure 6.2). The identification of this pattern has recently been confirmed by John Borland, who has been illustrating the corpus of Govan monuments.

<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/govan-2-b9dc56bfc1d342f6b4da3281e6629c07>

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Figure 6.2. Faint remnants of step pattern can be seen on the ridge of Govan 2, above the uppermost row of tile-pattern.

Kasten, Megan Nichole. 2019. 'The Govan Stones Revealed: Digital Imaging in the Analysis of Early Medieval Sculpture'. Doctoral Thesis (PhD), University of Glasgow.
<https://doi.org/10.5525/gla.thesis.74266>.

Hogback Govan Stone 2 @ Govan Old Parish Church, Glasgow, Scotland

Govan Stone 02 (Hogback)

Govan 2 (in both Stirling Maxwell's and ECMS numbering; Lang 1) is one of the smallest of Govan's five hogbacks and is the best preserved.

- [Related agents](#)
- [Creation](#)
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- [Related object structure](#)

Hogback Govan Stone 2 @ **Semantic Kompakkt**

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Item **Discussion**

Govan Stone 02 (Hogback) (Q1772)

Archaeological Artifact

▼ In more languages
Configure

Language	Label	Description
British English	No label defined	No description defined
English	Govan Stone 02 (Hogback)	Archaeological Artifact

► Mapping to other ontologies

Predicate	URL
-----------	-----

Statements

instance of Human-Made Object

▼ 0 references

Wikidata id Q136659904

▼ 0 references

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- Concept URI

Item **Discussion**

Govan Stone 02 (Hogback) (Q1773)

Govan 2 (in both Stirling Maxwell's and ECMS numbering; Lang 1) is one of the smallest of Govan's five hogbacks

▼ In more languages
Continue

Language	Label	Description
British English	No label defined	No description defined
English	Govan Stone 02 (Hogback)	Govan 2 (in both Stirling Maxwell's and ECMS numbering; Lang 1) is one of the smallest of Govan's five hogbacks and is the best preserved.

► Mapping to other ontologies

Predicate	URL
-----------	-----

Statements

instance of Media item

▼ 0 references

license Creative Commons Attribution

▼ 0 references

method Photogrammetry

▼ 0 references

software Agisoft Metashape

▼ 0 references

ZBrush

▼ 0 references

object of representation Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV

▼ 0 references

file view <https://semantic-kompakt.de/entity/6900db0bab8796a7fba84f05>

▼ 0 references

external link <https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/govan-2-b9dc56bfc1d342f6b4da3281e6629c07>

▼ 0 references

right held by Megan Nichole Kasten

▼ 0 references

contact person Florian Thierj

▼ 0 references

created by (event) Creation

carried out by **Megan Nichole Kasten**

▼ 0 references

Hogback Govan Stone 2 @ Semantic Kompakt Wikibase

Conclusion: Óghie and Squilly are able to create, maintain and publish research (meta)data within the Wikibase Ecosystem!

Finis!

Thx!

Florian Thiery M.Sc.
Research Squirrel Engineers Network
mail@fthiery.de
ORCID: 0000-0002-3246-3531